

Mathematical and numerical analysis of local buckling thin-walled beams with non-standard cross-sections

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ABSTRACT

The paper presents a novel approach to the analysis of buckling in thin-walled steel beams with modified cross-sectional shapes, focusing on their behavior under four-point bending. The aim of the study was to develop and examine new methods for determining critical loads for structural members with non-standard cross-sectional shapes, which are innovative in themselves. These methods are based on theoretical solutions grounded in the principle of potential energy conservation (an original approach). Additionally, based on the derived mathematical formulas, a custom application was developed, enabling rapid determination of critical loads using these new theoretical methods. The results show that the modified cross-sections significantly improve the mechanical properties of the beams, increasing their stiffness, buckling resistance, and load-bearing capacity. The findings provide new insights that can contribute to optimizing the design of thin-walled structures, with practical applications in the construction and automotive industries. The Finite Strip Method was used to verify the obtained results.

Keywords: thin-walled channel beam, local buckling, critical load, analytical study, finite strip method.

1. Introduction

Thin-walled structures are widely used in applications that require a high strength-to-weight ratio. In construction, they serve as steel profiles in industrial halls, bridges, roofs, and modular buildings. In aerospace, they form critical components of fuselages, wings, and aircraft skins. In automotive engineering, they enhance efficiency and safety in vehicle bodies, chassis, and safety cages. They are also essential in wind turbine towers, pipelines, and storage tanks in the energy sector, as well as in ship hulls in the maritime industry. Additionally, they are integral to the transport infrastructure and specialised designs demanding stiffness and low mass.

Despite advances in thin-walled structure analysis, many studies still focus on standard geometries like the lipped channel [1], [2], [3], one of the most widely researched cross-sections. In this work, the lipped channel serves as a reference to evaluate the performance of modified cross-sectional shapes. Comparing these non-standard geometries with the classic design highlights potential improvements in strength, stability, and efficiency, offering insights into how geometric modifications enhance structural behaviour.

Designing structures with modified cross-sections presents several challenges. Thin-walled structures are highly susceptible to instability, with complex interactions between buckling modes complicating stability analysis. Additionally, geometric imperfections significantly affect the results, making these structures difficult to analyze accurately [4]. Cold-forming, the only viable production method, is still difficult to automate. However, the use of modified cross-sections offers clear benefits, making further research valuable, as discussed in the work of Jasion et al. [5], Obst et al. [6] and Magnucka-Blandzi et al. [7]. These structures are more durable, allowing for fewer profiles and reduced material consumption, offering both engineering and ecological advantages. There are various methods to reinforce structures or their individual elements. The use of carbon nanotubes is one such method, as

44 described in the work of Sitli et al. [8]. The work by Pawlak et al. [9] describes the reinforcement of
45 structures using Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) tapes. Pingaro and Milani [10] described the
46 use of glass fibre-based composites for strengthening systems.

47 The most popular method for analyzing thin-walled profiles is numerical analysis, with the
48 Finite Element Method (FEM) commonly used for general structural analysis. However, the Finite Strip
49 Method (FSM), specifically developed for thin-walled profiles, is better suited to address their unique
50 characteristics, such as buckling and geometric imperfections. FSM provides a more efficient and
51 accurate approach for analyzing such structures. In the study by Zeinali et al. [11], the lateral-torsional
52 buckling of thin-walled channel-shaped PFRP beams under bending was analyzed using FEM numerical
53 modelling in Abaqus, highlighting the need for modified analytical equations for more accurate buckling
54 load prediction. Falkowicz [12] and in the study also used FEM and Abaqus to analyze thin-walled
55 channel-section composite profiles. In the study by Pham et al. [13], FEM and semi-analytical FSM
56 methods were used to investigate the elastic local buckling of thin-walled channel beams, including
57 lipped channels, under combined bending and shear stresses. Grenda and Paczos [14] also applied these
58 two methods (FEM and FSM) to analyze the behavior of thin-walled profiles with modified cross-
59 sectional shapes to determine their resistance to stability loss. Ajeesh and Jayachandran [15] calculated
60 the shear buckling stress of thin-walled sections using the constrained spline finite strip method. In the
61 paper [16], the Semi-Analytical Finite Strip Method (SAFSM) is presented for analyzing web crippling
62 in thin-walled sections under localized loading, validated against analytical, FEM, and SFSM solutions.
63 The study examines the buckling behaviour in plates and channel sections, highlighting the need to
64 obtain more series terms for accurate results under highly localised loading conditions. In work [17],
65 thin-walled, composite I beams are described, and a nonlinear, geometric buckling analysis is performed
66 using the finite element method, taking into account shear deformations and the influence of the ply
67 orientation on the composite structure.

68 Analytical calculations, or theoretical considerations, are widely used in the analysis of thin-
69 walled structures, forming the basis for many classical computational methods. However, existing
70 theoretical solutions do not always allow their application to structures with modified cross-sectional
71 shapes. In such cases, changes in the geometry of the cross-section introduce additional complexities,
72 making it difficult to directly apply traditional analytical equations. In the paper [18], the buckling of
73 thin-walled lipped channel columns with slotted webs was studied, focussing on the impact of shear
74 deformations. An analytical model was proposed to calculate the critical force, with numerical studies
75 confirming its accuracy. Martins et al. [19] studied lipped channel beams undergoing local-distortional
76 interaction are studied using a Generalized Beam Theory (GBT) based non-linear formulation, providing
77 mechanical characterization and insights to improve beam design under such effects. The GBT method
78 for analysing thin-walled profiles has also been applied in the studies by Bebiano et al. [20] and Duan
79 et al. [21]. In the study by Yu et al. [22], the critical stresses were determined using modified Hancock
80 formulas, as described in [23], where Hancock used the guidelines from the Australian/New Zealand
81 Standard for Cold-formed Steel Structures. The Eurocode 3 standard for the analysis of thin-walled
82 structures proposes the Effective Width Method (EWM), as discussed in the following studies Yao [24]
83 and Atya et al. [25].

84 This paper focusses on thin-walled steel beams with nonstandard cross-sectional shapes,
85 presenting innovative geometries that enhance structural performance. The research combines
86 theoretical considerations based on potential energy conservation with numerical analyses using the
87 Finite Strip Method (FSM), showing that these modified shapes significantly improve stiffness, leading
88 to higher critical and maximum load values. The literature review highlights a gap in research regarding
89 modified cross-sections, as current standards mainly address simple geometries. This work fills that gap

90 by introducing new cross-sectional shapes that offer improved performance, providing valuable insights
 91 for future structural design.

92

93 **2. Geometrical and material properties**

94 The cross-sections of the investigated beams are presented in Figure 1. The investigated beams have
 95 unconventional cross-sections; therefore, the following nomenclature is introduced: Lipped Channel
 96 Beam (LCB), Double Box Flanges Beam (DBFB), Double Box Flanges Beam and stiffened web with 3
 97 folds (DBFB-V), Double Box Flanges Beam and stiffened web with 4 folds
 98 (DBFB-S).

99

Fig. 1. Cross-sections of tested beams: (a) DBFB-V, (b) DBFB-S, (c) LCB, and (d) DBFB.

100 The research focusses on C beams with open cross-sections, which are thin-walled profiles of
 101 non-standard shape. The analysis was carried out on C beams with a length L of 400, 500, and 600 mm.
 102 The length L refers to the span between the supports, which is the section of the beam where the bending
 103 moment remains constant.

104

Table 1. Dimensions of the beams.

		Cross-sections [mm]			
Geometrical properties		LCB	DBFB	DBFB-V	DBFB-S
the depth of beam	H	160	160	160	160
the width of flange	b	80	80	80	80
the wall-thickness	t	1.00, 1.25	1.00, 1.25	1.00, 1.25	1.00, 1.25
the total length of beam	L_c	2000	2000	2000	2000
The length of the middle span	L	400, 500, 600	400, 500, 600	400, 500, 600	400, 500, 600
the length of stiffeners	c	-	20	26.5	26.5
the height of flanges	d	17	17	17	17
dimensions	e	-	14	14	14
the width of boxes	f	-	18	18	18

the distance between boxes	g	-	14	14	14
dimensions	k	-	-	5-50	5-50

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Table 1 presents the dimensions of the cross-sections of the analyzed beams shown in Figure 1. The analyses presented in this article, including both numerical and theoretical analyses, are studies that do not require the use of actual beams. However, in order for the results presented in this work to accurately reflect the real conditions, such profiles were fabricated through bending on semi-automatic or manual machines. Subsequently, the mechanical properties of the DX51 steel, from which the profiles were made, were investigated. The C-profiles were made of DX51 steel, hot-dip galvanized with a zinc coating of Z200-200 g/m² (Z200 according to EN 10025-2:2007). A static tensile test was performed, based on which the mechanical properties of this material were determined (Table 2).

Table 2. Mechanical properties of DX51 steel

Mechanical properties	Symbol	Value	Unit
Young's modulus	E	181	GPa
Upper yield limit	R_{eH}	339	MPa
Tensile strength	R_m	373	MPa
Poisson's ratio	ν	0,3	[/]

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116
117
118
119

Figure 2 shows the schematic of the testing setup, which simulates pure bending conditions. The setup was appropriately modelled and adapted to apply the corresponding boundary conditions in both the theoretical and numerical analyses (finite strip method).

Fig. 2. Beam loading scheme and longitudinal dimensions of the beam.

120

121 Experimental studies of four-point bending, where the focus was on thin-walled C
 122 profiles with a modified cross-sectional shape, are presented in the work of Grenda and Paczos
 123 [14].

124

125 3. Analytical study

126 The phenomenon of local buckling in cold-formed thin-walled beams is inherently linked to the
 127 geometrical configurations of their cross-sections. Using research by Silvestre and Camotim [26], one
 128 can effectively illustrate the progression of cross-section profile shaping through graphical
 129 representation, as exemplified in Figure 3. This study focusses on a simple supported cold-formed thin-
 130 walled beam characterised by a length L , a depth H and a wall thickness t , subjected to pure bending
 131 conditions (see Figure 2). The scheme of the cross-section with principal axes y - z with the origin $C(0,0)$
 132 is shown in Figure 3. The geometric properties of the cross-section are defined in Table 1.

133

Fig. 3. Scheme of the open mono-symmetrical C-sections of a thin-walled beam.

134

135 Theoretical analyses were conducted based on the basis of the principle of stationary potential
 136 energy. The variation in strain energy can be expressed as a function of the stress resultants acting on
 137 the cross-section of the thin-walled element. The variation of strain energy, U , is thus represented by the
 138 following equation.

139

$$U_{\varepsilon} = U_{\varepsilon l} + U_{\varepsilon n}, \quad (3.1)$$

140

141 in which, $U_{\varepsilon l}$ represents the linear part of the equation, and $U_{\varepsilon n}$ represents the nonlinear part of the
 142 equation. These components can be expressed using the following formulas:

143

$$U_{\varepsilon l} = \frac{1}{2} E \int_0^L \left[A \left(\frac{du}{dx} \right)^2 + J_z \left(\frac{d^2v}{dx^2} \right)^2 + 2J_{yz} \frac{d^2v}{dx^2} \frac{d^2w}{dx^2} + J_y \left(\frac{d^2w}{dx^2} \right)^2 + J_{\omega} \left(\frac{d^2\psi}{dx^2} \right)^2 \right] dx$$

$$+ \frac{1}{2} G \int_0^L J_t \left(\frac{d\psi}{dx} \right)^2 dx + \frac{1}{2} \int_0^L [k_y v_p^2 + k_z w_p^2 + k_{\psi} \psi^2] dx \quad (3.2)$$

$$U_{\text{en}} = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^L N \left[\left(\frac{dv}{dx} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{dw}{dx} \right)^2 \right] dx + \frac{1}{2} \int_0^L \left[r_S^2 N + 2\beta_{Sz} M_y - 2\beta_{Sy} M_z + 2\beta_{\omega} B \right] \left(\frac{d\psi}{dx} \right)^2 dx$$

$$+ \int_0^L \left[M_y \frac{d^2 v}{dx^2} + M_z \frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} \right] \psi dx + \int_0^L N \left[z_S \frac{dv}{dx} - y_S \frac{dw}{dx} \right] \frac{d\psi}{dx} dx,$$

144

145 where: u, v, w – displacement components of the shear centre S , u_P, v_P, w_P – displacement components

146 of the point P , ψ – torsion angle, A – cross-section area, J_y, J_{yz}, J_z – moments of inertia, J_{ω} – warping

147 constant, J_t – St-Venant torsion constant, r_S^2 – the polar moment of inertia about shear centre,

148 k_y, k_z, k_{ψ} – spring rates in the flange model for distortional buckling, $\beta_{Sy}, \beta_{Sz}, \beta_{\omega}$ – Wagner's

149 coefficients, N – axial force, M_y, M_z – bending moments about y and z axes, B – bimoment.

150

151 3.1. Global buckling

152 Analytical solutions of global buckling of a thin-walled beam with open cross-section, have been

153 presented in this paragraph. The positions of middle cross-sections of displacement for global buckling

154 of the beam is shown in Figure 4a.

Fig. 4. Scheme of displacement for (a) global buckling, (b) distortional buckling of the beam.

155

156 After inserting expressions (3.3) into Equation (3.1) and after integration, an expression

157 describing the strain energy of the beam in the form of:

158

$$N, M_z, B = 0, \quad J_{yz}, \beta_{Sz}, \beta_{\omega} = 0, \quad k_y, k_z, k_{\psi} = 0 \quad (3.3)$$

159

160 The strain energy U is developed according to Equations (3.1) and (3.3) becoming:

161

$$U_{\varepsilon} = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^L \left[EJ_z \left(\frac{d^2 v}{dx^2} \right)^2 + EJ_y \left(\frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} \right)^2 + EJ_{\omega} \left(\frac{d^2 \psi}{dx^2} \right)^2 + GJ_t \left(\frac{d\psi}{dx} \right)^2 \right] dx + \int_0^L M_y \frac{d^2 v}{dx^2} \psi dx \quad (3.4)$$

162

163 where $GJ_t, EJ_z, EJ_y, EJ_\omega$ is the torsional and flexural rigidity of the flange, $\psi(x)$ is the angle of the
 164 rotation of the flange (see Figure 4a), $v(x, y_1) = y_1\psi(x)$ is the corresponding transverse displacement-
 165 deflection, and the work of the load. The external load work W is defined by the relationship:
 166

$$W = -M_y \frac{dw}{dx} \Big|_0^L \quad (3.5)$$

167 where $w(x)$ is the displacement in the direction of the z axis, and $v(x)$ is the displacement in the direction
 168 of the y axis (see Figure 4), satisfying the equation with boundary conditions in which:
 169
 170

$$v(0) = w(0) = 0, \quad v(L) = w(L) = 0 \quad (3.6)$$

171 After inserting expressions defining the bending moment and the angle of rotation of the cross-
 172 -section of the beam deflections in the directions of the y axis and the z axis, respectively:
 173
 174

$$w(x) = \frac{M_0 L^2}{EJ_z} \left(\frac{1}{\pi^2} \sin \frac{\pi x}{L} \right) \psi_1, \quad (3.7)$$

$$v(x) = \frac{M_0 L^2}{4EJ_z} \left(\frac{1}{\pi^2} \sin^2 \frac{\pi x}{L} \right) \psi_1^2. \quad (3.8)$$

175 The work of loads is recorded:
 176
 177

$$W = \frac{\psi_1^2 L}{12\pi^2 EJ_z} \{ (2\pi^2 - 3)(2M_0^2) + 2(\pi^2 + 3)M_0^2 \} \quad (3.9)$$

178 The total potential energy is
 179
 180

$$\delta(U_\varepsilon - W) = 0, \quad (3.10)$$

181 a form of algebraic equation is obtained:
 182
 183

$$\frac{1}{6\pi^2} \{ 6\pi^2 M_0^2 \} = \frac{\pi^2}{L^2} EJ_z \left(\frac{\pi^2}{L^2} EJ_\omega + GJ_t \right). \quad (3.11)$$

184 The general stability condition for pure bending due to lateral buckling of the beam:
 185
 186

$$M_{cr}^{(global)} = \frac{\pi}{L} \sqrt{EJ_z \left[GJ_t + \left(\frac{\pi}{L} \right)^2 EJ_\omega \right]}. \quad (3.12)$$

187 3.2. Distortional buckling

188 A fundamental cold-formed thin-walled beam is characterised as a channel beam with flat flanges, the
 189 edges of which may remain unrestrained or be reinforced with bends. The phenomenon of buckling in
 190 such flanges has been extensively studied by numerous researchers, who have developed various
 191 equations specifically designed to calculate critical loads [27].
 192

193 To develop a simplified analytical model, a flat flange with bends is conceptualised as a long
 194 rectangular plate supported on three edges. Two of these edges are located at the beam's ends, whereas
 195 the third edge is at the junction between the flange and the web, aligned along the x -axis. The fourth
 196 edge, which is characterised by the bends, remains unrestrained. The width of the flange, denoted as b ,
 197 is much smaller than the length of the beam L . As a result, the variation in curvature across the width of
 198 the flange can be neglected, which allows a simplified displacement model. The displacement pattern
 199 associated with the distortional buckling of the beam is shown in Figure 4b. According to the classical
 200 theory of rectangular plate stability, the critical stress of the beam is expressed as follows:
 201

$$\sigma_x(x, \bar{y}, \bar{z}) = \frac{M_y}{J_y} (\bar{z} - \bar{z}_C) \quad (3.13)$$

202 where (\bar{y}, \bar{z}) is the central coordinate system connected to the flange of beam. The internal forces that
 203 occur in the beam flange can be expressed as follows.
 204

$$\bar{N} = -\frac{M_y}{J_y} \bar{z}_C \bar{A}, \quad \bar{M}_{\bar{y}} = \frac{M_y}{J_y} \bar{J}_{\bar{y}}, \quad \bar{M}_{\bar{z}} = -\frac{M_y}{J_y} \bar{J}_{\bar{y}\bar{z}}, \quad \bar{B} = 0. \quad (3.14)$$

205 after simplification $\bar{v}_P = 0$, $\bar{w}_P = 0$ and $k_\psi = 0$ can be written as:
 206
 207

$$\bar{v} = (\bar{z}_P - \bar{z}_{\bar{s}}) \bar{\psi}, \quad \bar{w} = -(\bar{y}_P - \bar{y}_{\bar{s}}) \bar{\psi} \quad (3.15)$$

208 The strain energy of the beam flange after the internal forces is put into Equation (3.1) equals:
 209
 210

$$U_\varepsilon = \frac{1}{2} E \bar{J}_{\bar{\omega}_P} \int_0^L \left(\frac{d^2 \bar{\psi}}{dx^2} \right)^2 dx + \frac{1}{2} G \bar{J}_t \int_0^L \left(\frac{d \bar{\psi}}{dx} \right)^2 dx \\ - \frac{1}{2} \frac{M_y}{I_y} [\bar{r}_P^2 \bar{z}_C \bar{A} - 2 \bar{\beta}_{P\bar{z}} \bar{J}_{\bar{y}} - 2 \bar{\beta}_{P\bar{y}} \bar{J}_{\bar{y}\bar{z}}] \int_0^L \left(\frac{d \bar{\psi}}{dx} \right)^2 dx, \quad (3.16)$$

211 where:
 212
 213

$$\bar{r}_P^2 = \frac{\bar{J}_{\bar{y}} + \bar{J}_{\bar{z}}}{\bar{A}} + \bar{y}_P^2 + \bar{z}_P^2, \\ \bar{J}_{\bar{\omega}_P} = \bar{J}_{\bar{\omega}} + (\bar{y}_P - \bar{y}_{\bar{s}})^2 \bar{J}_{\bar{y}} - 2(\bar{y}_P - \bar{y}_{\bar{s}})(\bar{z}_P - \bar{z}_{\bar{s}}) \bar{J}_{\bar{y}\bar{z}} + (\bar{z}_P - \bar{z}_{\bar{s}})^2 \bar{J}_{\bar{z}}, \\ \bar{\beta}_{P\bar{y}} = \bar{\beta}_{\bar{s}\bar{y}} + \bar{y}_{\bar{s}} - \bar{y}_P, \quad \bar{\beta}_{P\bar{z}} = \bar{\beta}_{\bar{s}\bar{z}} + \bar{z}_{\bar{s}} - \bar{z}_P. \quad (3.17)$$

214 The critical moment is calculated from the following equation:
 215
 216

$$\delta(U_\varepsilon) = 0, \quad (3.18)$$

217 in which
 218
 219

$$\bar{\psi}(x) = \psi_1 \sin \frac{\pi x}{L}. \quad (3.19)$$

220

221 Finally, the critical moment was calculated according to the Ritz method:
 222

$$M_{cr}^{(distortional)} = \frac{G\bar{J}_t + E\bar{J}_{\omega_p} \left(\frac{\pi}{L}\right)^2}{\bar{r}_p^2 \bar{z}_c \bar{A} - 2\bar{\beta}_{p\bar{y}} \bar{J}_{\bar{y}} - 2\bar{\beta}_{p\bar{z}} \bar{J}_{\bar{y}\bar{z}}} J_y. \quad (3.20)$$

223
 224 The regional and distortional buckling issues have been elucidated in numerous scholarly
 225 articles. Samanta and Kumar [28] have examined the local buckling of mono-symmetrical I-beams.
 226 They have observed that local buckling plays a particularly significant role in the behaviour of short
 227 beams, where it also limits the critical load. The flanges of the thin-walled beams are treated as
 228 rectangular plates with three simply supported edges and one free edge. These flanges, in bending
 229 beams, are typically subjected to longitudinal compression. The buckling of the flanges involves both
 230 bending and torsional effects.

231
 232 **3.3. Local buckling**

233 The theoretical critical stresses (elastic buckling) of the web are as follows: four simply supported edges
 234 – span structure (see Figure 5a); three simply supported edges and one free edge – cantilevered structure
 235 (see Figure 5b-c) [27].
 236

Fig. 5. Scheme of simply supported beams.

237 The potential energies of elastic strains are as follows:
 238

$$U_\varepsilon = U_{el} + U_{en}, \quad (3.21)$$

239
 240 where:

$$U_{el} = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^L \int_0^h \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial^2 \tilde{w}}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \tilde{w}}{\partial \eta^2} \right)^2 - 2(1-\nu) \left[\frac{\partial^2 \tilde{w}}{\partial x^2} \frac{\partial^2 \tilde{w}}{\partial \eta^2} - \left(\frac{\partial^2 \tilde{w}}{\partial x \partial \eta} \right)^2 \right] \right\} d\eta dx, \quad (3.22)$$

$$U_{en} = \frac{1}{2} t \int_0^L \int_0^h \sigma_x \left(\frac{\partial \tilde{w}}{\partial x} \right)^2 d\eta dx, \quad (3.23)$$

241
 242 and (x, η, ζ) is the local coordinate system associated with the beam wall, \tilde{w} the deflection of the wall
 243 towards ζ , \tilde{w} , σ_x is the stress. The method of Ritz, where the deflection is approximated, is a function:
 244

$$\tilde{w}(x, \eta) = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} w_{mn} \sin \frac{m\pi x}{L} \sin \frac{n\pi \eta}{h}, \quad (3.24)$$

245
246 where the potential energy is:
247

$$U_{\varepsilon} = \frac{1}{2} w^T (K_L - K_G) w, \quad (3.25)$$

248
249 where:
250

$$w^T = [w_{11}, w_{12}, \dots, w_{1n_{max}}, w_{21}, \dots, w_{m_{max}n_{max}}] \quad (3.26)$$

251
252 Considering the classical theory of stability, stationary energy of potential energy:
253

$$\delta(U_{\varepsilon l} + U_{\varepsilon n}) = 0 \quad (3.27)$$

254 After transformation above equation:
255

$$\delta(K_L + K_G) = 0 \quad (3.28)$$

256
257 K_L and K_G are diagonal matrices corresponding to the linear and nonlinear terms, respectively, defined
258 as in the case of span structure:
259

$$[K_L]_{ij} = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{m^2}{\lambda} + n^2 \lambda \right)^2, & \text{for } m = k \text{ and } n = l \\ 0, & \text{for otherwise} \end{cases}$$

and

$$[K_G]_{ij} = \begin{cases} m^2 \left(1 - \frac{\beta}{2} \right), & \text{for } m = k \text{ and } n = l \\ 4\beta \frac{m^2}{\pi^2} \frac{nl}{(n^2 - l^2)^2} [(-1)^{n+l} - 1], & \text{for } m = k \text{ and } n \neq l \\ 0, & \text{for otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3.29)$$

the indices are calculated as follows:

$$i = (m - 1)n_{max} + n$$

$$j = (k - 1)n_{max} + l$$

where $m, k = 1, 2, \dots, m_{max}$ and $n, l = 1, 2, \dots, n_{max}$ or conversely.

$$m = \left[\frac{i}{n_{max}} \right], \quad n = [(i - 1) \bmod n_{max}] + 1$$

$$k = \left[\frac{j}{n_{max}} \right], \quad l = [(j - 1) \bmod n_{max}] + 1$$

where $i, j = 1, 2, \dots, m_{max}, n_{max}$.

260
261 In the case of cantilevered structure, point R lies at the junction of the studied panel with another
262 panel of the cross-section (case I) or at its free end (case II):
263

$$[K_L]_{mk} = \begin{cases} m^2 \left(\frac{6}{\pi^2} (1 - \nu) + \frac{m^2}{\lambda^2} \right), & \text{for } m = k \\ 0, & \text{for otherwise} \end{cases}$$

where $m, k = 1, 2, \dots, m_{max}$.

K_G in the I case can be define as:

$$[K_G]_{mk} = \begin{cases} m^2 \left(1 - \frac{3}{4} \beta \right), & \text{for } m = k \\ 0, & \text{for otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3.30)$$

and in II case:

$$[K_G]_{mk} = \begin{cases} m^2 \left(1 - \frac{1}{4} \beta \right), & \text{for } m = k \\ 0, & \text{for otherwise} \end{cases}$$

264

265 Parameter κ is the coefficient depending on the ratio of wall dimensions $\lambda = \frac{L}{h}$ and parameter β . For the
266 span wall, the stresses are as follows:

267

$$\sigma_x(x, \eta) = - \left(1 - \frac{\eta}{h} \right) \sigma_1 - \frac{\eta}{h} \sigma_2 = -\sigma_1 \left[\left(1 - \frac{\eta}{h} \right) + \frac{\eta}{h} \psi \right] \quad (3.31)$$

268

269 In which $\sigma_1 = \max(-\sigma_x) > 0$ and $\sigma_1 = \kappa \frac{\pi^2 D}{t h^2} = \kappa \frac{\pi^2 E}{12(1-\nu^2)} \left(\frac{t}{h} \right)^2$. For the cantilevered wall simply
270 supported edge is for $\eta = 0$ and free edge is for $\eta = h$. Two cases are considered when:

271

- I case – when $\sigma_x(x, 0) = \sigma_1$ and $\sigma_x(x, h) = \sigma_2$,

272

- II case – when $\sigma_x(x, 0) = \sigma_2$ and $\sigma_x(x, h) = \sigma_1$.

273

The stresses are as follows:

274

$$\sigma_x = - \begin{cases} \left(1 - \frac{\eta}{h} \right) \sigma_1 + \frac{\eta}{h} \sigma_2 \\ \left(1 - \frac{\eta}{h} \right) \sigma_2 + \frac{\eta}{h} \sigma_1 \end{cases} = -\sigma_1 \times \begin{cases} \left(1 - \frac{\eta}{h} \right) + \frac{\eta}{h} \psi, & \text{for I case} \\ \left(1 - \frac{\eta}{h} \right) \psi + \frac{\eta}{h}, & \text{for II case} \end{cases} \quad (3.32)$$

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276 Solving equation (3.27) using the Ritz method, where the approximate deflection is a function:

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$$\tilde{w}(x, \eta) = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} w_m \eta \sin \frac{m\pi x}{L} \quad (3.33)$$

278

279 where L is the length of the middle span. We get the critical values of κ coefficient:

280

$$\kappa_{cr} = \left(\frac{6}{\pi^2} (1 - \nu) + \frac{1}{\lambda^2} \right) \times \begin{cases} \frac{4}{1 + 3\psi}, & \text{for I case} \\ \frac{4}{3 + \psi}, & \text{for II case} \end{cases} \quad (3.34)$$

281

282 for $\psi_L \leq \psi \leq 1$, where $\psi_L \cong -0.2$ for I case and $\psi_L \cong -2.3$ for II case. The stresses are as follows:

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$$\sigma_{y,cr} = \kappa_{cr} \frac{\pi^2 E}{12(1-\nu^2)} \left(\frac{t}{b}\right)^2 \quad (3.35)$$

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and b - width of the shelf, κ is a coefficient depending on the dimension of wall dimensions $\lambda = \frac{L}{b}$ and parameter β . The local stability is calculated for each beam wall where compressive stresses occur. The critical moment of local buckling for case I can be saved in the form:

$$M_{y,cr}^{(local)} = \frac{J_y}{y_R} \left(\frac{6}{\pi^2} (1-\nu) + \frac{1}{\lambda^2} \right) \times \frac{4}{1+3\psi} \times \frac{\pi^2 E}{12(1-\nu^2)} \left(\frac{t}{b}\right)^2 \quad (3.36)$$

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where $R(y_R, z_R)$ is the point lying at one of the ends of the centre line of the wall, where the compressive stresses have the highest value denoted by σ_1 , at the other end of the tension we denote σ_2 . Solving the Equation (3.28) results are presented in the graph (see Figure 6). It presents the values of the κ_{cr} parameter depending on ψ . The ratio of the wall length to its width for pure bending, designated later as σ_{cr} is 1000.

Fig. 6. The critical value of κ coefficient depending on ψ .

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Based on the above formulas, an original GUI CriticalForcesBeams was developed (the programme was written in MATLAB), which allows for the determination of critical moments for four-point bent beams with a modified cross-sectional shape. The interface of the application is shown in Figure 7. It is evident that the programme calculates the critical moment values based on the formulas derived in this chapter and provides these values for all modes of buckling: general, local, and distortional. The programme allows for the adjustment of the geometric dimensions of the cross-sections

302 of the beams as well as their lengths. It is clear that the beams analysed in this work will experience
 303 local or distortional loss of stability. However, the programme has been designed in such a way that it
 304 is possible to analyse beams of varying lengths, and thus beams that undergo different modes of
 305 buckling. This approach enables a comprehensive analysis of the issue at hand.
 306

Fig. 7. Programme GUI CriticalForcesBeams.

307 The values of the critical moments obtained from the calculations carried out in this programme
 308 are shown below. Finally, the critical moment is the minimum value from the moments calculated
 309 according to Equation (3.7). It results from the above considerations that in the analysis of the stress
 310 state, it is important to determine the values of geometrical quantities characterising the cross-section of
 311 a thin-wall beam. The patterns obtained describing the critical stresses were then used to determine the
 312 critical load values for the sections analysed. The theoretical critical moments of the flange and the web
 313 of beams with different cross-sections are given in Table 3.
 314

Table 3. Values of the critical moment of flange and web – analytical solutions.

t [mm]	1.00	1.10	1.20	1.25	1.00	1.10	1.20	1.25
M_{cr} [kNm]	M_{cr} of flange				M_{cr} of web			
LCB	2.60	2.48	3.69	4.01	3.01	3.65	5.44	5.91
DBFB	3.98	5.28	6.85	7.73	6.02	7.29	10.69	11.45
DBFB-V	4.01	5.33	6.91	7.80	6.17	7.48	11.16	12.12

DBFB-S	4.18	5.55	7.19	8.12	6.27	7.60	11.29	12.26
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The results of the numerical analyses, that is, the critical moments, are presented in Table 3. They confirmed that the shape of the cross-section had a great influence on the values of those moments. The least strong were standard channel beams without double box flanges and stiffened web (LCB and DBFB), while the strongest were double box flange beams with stiffened web (DBFB-V and DBFB-S). The differences between critical forces ranged from 0.5% to 14% in the case of beams of wall-thickness $t = 1.00 \text{ mm}$ and from 0% to 14.7% for the beams of wall-thickness $t = 1.25 \text{ mm}$.

3.4. Parametric study of a section with a double box on the flange

The analyses conducted revealed that the highest critical moment values were achieved for the section that features double flange boxes combined with a modified web shape. Consequently, a parametric analysis was undertaken to examine the influence of the modification shape located on the flange with four folds (DBFB-S). The parameter under investigation is the length of the flat part of the web, denoted as a_1 in the program. This parameter is illustrated in Figure 8.

Fig. 8. Shape of the cross-section in relation to the decrease of the parameter a_1 .

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Figure 8 illustrates the cross-sectional shapes corresponding to different values of the parameter a_1 . The analyses were performed using the GUI CriticalForcesBeams, which incorporates the mathematical formulas outlined in Chapter 3. For the actual beam, the parameter a_1 is set to 40 mm. Within the parametric study, the value of this parameter was progressively reduced in increments of 5 mm, culminating in a value of 0 mm.

The objective of this investigation is to evaluate the impact of the beam web bend shape on the critical moment. As mentioned above, the program calculates the critical moment values for three distinct buckling modes. These results are presented in Table 4 and are graphically depicted in Figure 9. Additionally, the programme enables modifications to the beam length L . However, for the current study, the length L was fixed at 400 mm.

Table 4. Values of the critical moments depending on the parameter a_1 .

a_1 [mm]	Critical moment [kNm]		
	global buckling	distortional buckling	local buckling
40	401.83	75.62	4.65
35	406.83	75.98	4.67
30	411.52	76.24	3.99
25	415.95	76.41	3.54
20	420.15	76.54	3.24

15	424.21	76.28	3.06
10	428.22	76.89	2.99
5	432.30	77.23	3.03
0 (1)	435.70	77.66	3.16

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Fig. 9. Values of critical moments depending on the parameter a_1 .

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The parametric study revealed that as the parameter a_1 decreases, there is a corresponding increase in the critical moments associated with both global and distortional buckling. In contrast, for local buckling, the critical moment values exhibit a decreasing trend with the reduction in a_1 . However, at a specific value of 15 mm, the critical moment stabilizes and remains constant at 3.0 kNm.

It should be noted that the highest critical moment values are observed for global buckling, whereas the lowest values are associated with local buckling. Importantly, in thin-walled structural configurations, local buckling emerges as the predominant and most critical mode of instability. This conclusion is strongly supported by the observed critical moment values.

The critical moments (in kNm) associated with various buckling modes – local, distortional, and global – have been thoroughly analysed for five distinct cross-sections, all maintaining an identical cross-sectional area. These results are presented comprehensively in Table 5. Notably, the critical moments for global buckling consistently exhibit the highest values across all evaluated cross-sections, indicating that global stability is the predominant mode of structural resistance within the parameters analysed.

Among the examined cross-sections, cross-section 3 demonstrates the highest global buckling moment, recorded at 471.7 kNm, followed by cross-sections 4 and 5, which also show substantial values. Resistance to distortional buckling is observed exclusively in cross-sections 3, 4, and 5, while cross-sections 1 and 2 do not display any evidence of such behaviour, emphasizing a distinct variation in buckling characteristics.

365 The critical moments associated with local buckling are lower in comparison to global buckling,
 366 but exhibit significant variability across the cross-sections. This variability suggests that certain
 367 geometric configurations, particularly those of cross-sections 4 and 5, may enhance local stability. These
 368 findings are further illustrated in Figure 10, which provides a clear graphical representation of the critical
 369 moments and their implications for structural performance.
 370

Table 5. Values of critical moments vs. different beams with the same cross-sectional areas.

Steel sheet Thickness	Cross Sections	Critical moment [kNm]			[mm]
		Global Buckling	Distortional Buckling	Local Buckling	
$t = 2.157$ mm	1	396.40	0.00	2.34	$(a_1=0)$
$t = 2.135$ mm	2	358.50	0.00	2.29	$(a_1=40)$
$t = 2.000$ mm	3	471.70	6.80	17.63	$(a_1=40)$
$t = 1.066$ mm	4	434.36	77.43	5.40	$(a_1=0)$
$t = 1.000$ mm	5	401.83	75.62	5.47	$(a_1=40)$

onstans $A_0 = 688 \text{ mm}^2$

371

Fig. 10. Critical moments vs. different beams with the same cross-sectional areas

372 Based on the studies conducted by Amali and Anbarasu [29], as well as Zhong et al. [30],
 373 normalised slenderness values were determined for various materials and cross-sectional shapes of the
 374 beams analysed.

375 The study by Amali and Anbarasu [29] presented numerical analyses examining the behaviour
 376 of innovative cold-formed steel (CFS) built-up beams, designed as closed I-beams composed of four
 377 plain channels, under simply supported end conditions. The researchers proposed design adjustments to
 378 enhance the accuracy of predictions on the beams' flexural strength and behaviour of the beams. These
 379 recommendations were validated through reliability analyses, demonstrating their effectiveness in

380 modelling complex buckling behaviours in CFS built-up I-beams. The investigation by Zhong et al. [30]
 381 focused on the local buckling behaviour and capacities of hexagonal hollow stainless steel sections,
 382 using experimental and numerical methods. The findings were evaluated against the buckling design
 383 rules outlined in the European code, the American specification, and the ASCE standard. A modified
 384 ASCE approach was proposed, resulting in improved accuracy in cross-section classification and
 385 resistance predictions.

386 The results of the analyses conducted based on the methodologies from the above studies are
 387 presented in Table 6 and Figures 11, 12, and 13.

388 Table 6. shows codified slenderness limits, where $\varepsilon_{EC3} = \sqrt{235/\sigma_{0,2}}$, $\varepsilon_{AISC} = \sqrt{E/\sigma_{0,2}}$ and
 389 $\varepsilon_{ASCE} = \sqrt{1/\sigma_{0,2}}$.

390

Table 6. Codified slenderness limits.

Code	Slenderness limit
EN 1993-1-4	$37 \cdot \varepsilon_{EC3}$
AISC 370-21	$1.24 \cdot \varepsilon_{AISC}$
ASCE/SEI 48-11	$681.2 \cdot \varepsilon_{ASCE}$

391

392 Grenda and Paczos [14] investigated cold-formed, thin-walled channel beams with non-standard
 393 cross-sections, focusing on their local elastic buckling and limit load under pure bending conditions.
 394 The work combines numerical analyses using the Finite Element Method (FEM) and Finite Strip Method
 395 (FSM) with experimental investigations to validate mathematical models. The study includes more than
 396 80 beam samples, with experiments conducted at Poznan University of Technology, using cold-formed
 397 steel sheets made of steel sheet DX51. The results indicate that new cross-sectional designs can improve
 398 the strength and stability of thin-walled beams, contributing to advances in structural engineering. Figure
 399 11. shows a comparison of slenderness for different materials. The use of steel DX51 has allowed for a
 400 significant increase in slenderness for all types of cross-section.

401

402
403 **Fig. 11.** Normalised slenderness for different materials and structural shapes.
404

405 The evaluations of the slenderness limit, as depicted in Figure 12, are based on three standards:
406 EC3, AISC, and ASCE. The figure presents the load capacities and critical forces corresponding to
407 various structural shapes. The DBFB configurations (DBFB, DBFB-V, and DBFB-S) consistently
408 exhibit high values across all standards, highlighting their efficiency in withstanding compression loads.

409
410 **Fig. 12.** Evaluation of the EC3, AISC, ASCE slenderness limit for internal plate elements in
411 compression.

413 **Fig. 13.** Comparison of the slenderness and effective width for different materials.
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416 The relationship between effective width and slenderness for various materials is illustrated in
 417 Figure 13. The analysis highlights a trend where higher effective widths correspond to lower slenderness
 418 ratios, particularly in aluminium materials and lower-strength steels. DBFB configurations maintain
 419 high slenderness values, indicating that this shape offers enhanced structural stability in slender
 420 members. On the contrary, the LBC shape exhibits lower slenderness values, signifying reduced
 421 structural efficiency in accommodating high slenderness ratios under compression.
 422

423 **4. Numerical study - analysis of the beam**

424 Cold-formed steel profiles were analyzed using the Finite Strip Method (FSM) with CUFSM software
 425 version 4.05. The cross-sections are presented in Figure 1. Lipped channel sections, a classic C-profile
 426 type, increase load-bearing capacity, strength, and stability without significantly increasing mass,
 427 making them widely used in civil engineering and industry. The masses of the profiles analysed along
 428 with their geometric characteristics are shown in Table 7.
 429

Table 7. The masses of the beams and the moment of inertia of the cross-sections of the analyzed beams.

Beam	Wall thickness $t[mm]$	Mass $[kg]$	Moment of Inertia $I_y[cm^4]$
LCB	1.00	5.20	154.8
	1.25	6.50	193.5
DBFB	1.00	8.36	299.5
	1.25	10.45	370.1
DBFB-V	1.00	10.20	317.5
	1.25	12.75	396.6
DBFB-S	1.00	10.10	322.6
	1.25	12.63	403.2

430 Figure 14 compares the influence of wall thicknesses $t=1.00$ mm and $t=1.25$ mm on the
 431 relationship between the load factor and the half-wave length for the DBFB-V beam. It is concluded that
 432 lipped flanges and web stiffeners enhance beam stiffness and stability. The critical forces increase
 433 slightly with the intermediate length of the span (L), though L has a minimal effect on the critical stresses
 434 (less than 3%). Longer spans result in more half-waves, but wall thickness and web stiffeners do not
 435 affect the number of half-waves. Computational analyses reveal interactions between the buckling
 436 modes of the flanges and the web, aiding in the development of more accurate analytical models. These
 437 findings support the exploration of novel alternatives to standardised cross-sections of cold-formed thin-
 438 walled beams.

Fig. 14. Relationship between the length of half-wave and the load factor for DBFB-V with two different wall thicknesses.

439 The cross-section of the DBFB-S beam is shown in Figure 1. Boxed flanges enhance the beam's
 440 load capacity, strength, and stability without significantly increasing its weight. Figure 15 illustrates the
 441 relationship between the load factor, the half-wave length and buckling mode for the DBFB-S beam
 442 (FSM analysis). Table 8 presents the numerical critical loads for thin-walled beams with modified C-
 443 sections, which align with the analytical solutions derived from the critical loads of the web and flange.
 444 Analytical models of local buckling, found in the literature, helped estimate the upper and lower bounds
 445 of the numerical solutions. The discrepancy between the numerical and theoretical critical moments did
 446 not exceed 14.7%, indicating satisfactory agreement between the results.
 447

Fig. 15. Buckled shapes for CUFSM results (DBFB-S).

Table 8. The critical stress based on numerical results.

Beam	LCB	DBFB	DBFB-V	DBFB-S
Thickness $t = 1.00$ mm				
Critical stress - σ_{cr}				
numerical analysis	134.0	138.5	153.6	158.0
Thickness $t = 1.25$ mm				
Critical stress - σ_{cr}				
numerical analysis	209.0	215.0	242.0	243.1
Buckling mode	distortional	flange local	flange local	flange local

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The results, including critical forces, stresses, and corresponding buckling modes obtained using the Finite Strip Method, are presented in tables and figures. The impact of cross-sectional morphology, web stiffeners, and wall thickness on the number of half-waves is also analysed. The beams were subjected to a constant bending moment along their entire length. The DBFB-V and DBFB-S beams consist of 20 elements and 21 nodes, with loading applied such that the critical forces are equal to the calculated load factors multiplied by 100. To validate the numerical results, certain computations were repeated with double- and quadrupled strips. The best results were obtained when the DBFB, DBFB-V, and DBFB-S beams comprised approximately 120 strips, although the computation time and discrepancies between results were also considered. The number of elements and nodes depends on the configuration of the cross-section of the slender-walled channel beams.

5. Conclusions

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The manuscript presents an analysis of cold-formed thin-walled channel beams with non-standard cross-sections using both analytical and numerical methods (FSM). Examines four different beam cross-sections subjected to pure bending, focussing on their linear elastic stability and ultimate load. The goal is to compare numerical results, obtained with CUFSM, for these modified cross-sections. This helps to confirm the accuracy of numerical models for pure bending and provides insight into buckling modes of flanges and webs. However, since numerical models are based on assumptions and simplifications, their results should be validated with experimental data in future studies.

Table 9 and Figure 16 present a comparison of the critical load values obtained from analytical solutions and numerical analyses.

Table 9. Comparison of critical stress for analytical solutions and numerical results.

Beam	LCB	DBFB	DBFB-V	DBFB-S
Thickness $t = 1.00$ mm				
Critical stress - σ_{cr}				
analytical solution	152.8	156.0	155.3	158.8
numerical analysis	134.0	138.5	153.6	158.0
error (%)	12.3	11.2	1.1	0.5
Thickness $t = 1.25$ mm				
Critical stress - σ_{cr}				
analytical solution	239.0	238.9	242.0	243.0
numerical analysis	209.0	215.0	242.0	243.1
error (%)	12.5	10.0	0.0	0.04
<i>Buckling mode</i>	<i>distortional</i>	<i>flange local</i>	<i>flange local</i>	<i>flange local</i>

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- 474 On the basis of the numerical analysis and the analytical solution, it was determined that
 475 • The web bends in the DBFB, DBFB-V, and DBFB-S profiles increase the strength of the
 476 structure compared to beams without a bent web: approximately 45% for a wall thickness of
 477 $t = 1.00$ mm and approximately 43% for a wall thickness of $t = 1.25$ mm.
 478 • The value of critical loads increases slightly with the growth of the middle span dimension L .
 479 The dimension of the L span affects the number of buckling half-waves, a larger span results in
 480 more half-waves, regardless of the wall thickness or web reinforcement.
 481 • For beams with a lip on the flange, the values of the critical forces decrease slightly.

482 Numerical analyses complement the analytical solution. The difference between the numerical
 483 and analytical results is less than 14.7%. The proposed double box flanges in open profiles demonstrate
 484 greater resistance to buckling compared to traditional flat flanges. The dimension L does not
 485 significantly affect the values of the critical loads, but it does influence the number of buckling half-
 486 waves: as the span increases, the number of half-waves also increases.

487 A parametric analysis, which involved modifying the dimension a_1 in the DBFB-S section
 488 beam, determined that:

- 489 • As the dimension a_1 decreases, the value of critical moments for global and distortional
 490 buckling increases.
 491 • For local buckling, the critical moment decreases and stabilizes at $a_1 = 15$ mm.

492 In Figure 16, the computational results for four different beams were juxtaposed. The minimum
 493 and maximum values of the derived critical forces were illustrated.

Fig. 16. Analytical and numerical relationship between wall thickness and critical moment.

494 They substantiated that beams with reinforced webs and intricate flanges constructed from
 495 several bends exhibited greater strength than those with more straightforward flanges. Extension along
 496 the webs also improved the strength of the beams. The strength of beams with double box flanges (DBFB
 497 - double box flanges beam) was comparable to the strength of beams with double box flanges and
 498 reinforced webs (DBFB-V and DBFB-S).

- 499 • The results confirm the validity of exploring new geometries for cold-formed thin-walled beam
 500 cross-sections.

- 501 • Modern technologies enable the production of various geometries for thin-walled beams that
- 502 meet market demands, research needs, and environmental considerations, such as reducing
- 503 material consumption in construction.

504

505 **Notation**

506

507 k_y, k_z, k_ψ – spring rates in the flange model for distortional buckling

508 J_y, J_{yz}, J_z – moments of inertia of the cross-section

509 u, v, w – shear center displacement S

510 u_R, v_R, w_R – displacement components of the point R

511 u_P, v_P, w_P – displacement components of the point P

512 x, y, z – basic beam coordinate system

513 x, \bar{y}, \bar{z} – central coordinate system connected to the flange of beam with the middle at point \bar{C}

514 $\beta_{sz}, \beta_{sy}, \beta_\omega$ – Wagner’s coefficients

515 x, η, ζ – local coordinate system

516 K_L, K_G – diagonal matrices referring to the linear equation and the nonlinear equation

517 M_y, M_z – bending moments about y and z axes

518 y_R, z_R – coordinates of the point R , lying at one end of the midline of the wall

519 y_S, z_S – coordinates of the shear center S

520 A – cross-sectional area of the beam

521 b – width of the beam

522 B – bimoment

523 c – length of the stiffeners

524 C – center of gravity of the beam cross-section

525 \bar{C} – center of gravity of the flange

526 C' – displaced center of gravity of the beam cross-section for overall buckling

527 d – height of the flanges

528 e – dimension of the beam

529 E – Young’s modulus

530 f – width of the boxes

531 F_{cr} – critical force

532 g – distance between boxes

533 G – Kirchhoff modulus

534 H – depth of the beam

535 J_t – the Saint-Venant torsion constant

536 J_ω – warping constant

537 L – the length of the middle span subjected to pure bending

538 L_c – total length of the beam

539 k – dimension of the beam

540 M_0 – external moment applied at the ends of the beam

541 M_{cr} – critical moment

542 M_g – bending moment

543 N – axial force

544 r_S^2 – polar radius of inertia about the shear center S

545 $R_{eH} = f_{yb}$ – yield strength

546 $R_m = f_u$ – ultimate strength

547 t – thickness

548 U_ε – elastic deformation energy

549 $U_{\varepsilon n}$ – nonlinear elastic deformation energy

550 $U_{\varepsilon l}$ – linear elastic deformation energy

551 W – work of external forces

552 \tilde{w} – the deflection of the wall towards ζ
553 \bar{z}_C – the coordinate of the beam section center in the coordinate system associated with the flange
554 κ – the coefficient depending on the ratio of wall dimensions $\lambda = \frac{L}{h}$ and parameter β
555 κ_{cr} – the critical coefficient depending on the ratio of wall dimensions $\lambda = \frac{L}{h}$ and parameter β
556 λ – slenderness of the beam
557 ν – Poisson’s ratio
558 ρ – mass density
559 σ_g – bending stress
560 σ_x – normal stress in the x-axis direction
561 ψ – torsion angle
562 ψ_1 – dimensionless parameter
563

564 **CRedit statements**

565 **Aleksandra M. Pawlak:** Validation, Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review &
566 Editin, Formal analysis, Visualization. **Piotr Paczos:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision,
567 Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Michał Grenda:** Conceptualization, Methodology,
568 Software, Validation, Resources, Writing - Original Draft, Visualization. **Tomasz Górný:** Validation,
569 Writing – original draft, Writing - Review & Editing. **Marcin Rodak:** Methodology, Resources,
570 Software, Formal analysis.

571

572 **Acknowledgments**

573 The project was funded by the National Science Centre allocated on the basis of the decision No. DEC-
574 2021/43/B/ST8/00845 of 2022-05-23 – Contract No. UMO-2021/43/B/ST8/00845.

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